

ALL-Ready – The European Agroecology
Living Lab and Research Infrastructure Network: preparation phase

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Policy briefs for regional, national and EU-level policy makers

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List of abbreviations

BÖL	Federal Organic Farming Scheme
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
EIP Agri	European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
Partnership AGROECOLOGY	Horizon Europe Partnership "Accelerating farming systems transition: agroecology living labs and research infrastructures"
WP	Work package

1. Introduction

ALL-Ready is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) funded by the European Commission (EC) with the aim of preparing a framework for a future European Network of Living Labs and Research Infrastructures that will enable the transition towards agroecology throughout Europe. Based on the premise that agroecology can strengthen the sustainability and resilience of farming systems, the project will contribute to addressing the multiple challenges that they are facing today including climate change, loss of biodiversity, dwindling resources, degradation of soil and water quality.

1.1 Purpose of the Deliverable

This deliverable (D) focuses on and summarises the ALL-Ready recommendations for policy-makers and funders (as well as communities of living labs and research infrastructures) in the form of policy briefs. The purpose and approach to the development of the briefs is summarised, their dissemination outlined and links to the final documents provided.

1.2 Policy briefs: Purpose and process of development

The purpose of the policy briefs was to disseminate key lessons and recommendations for policy (including research policies and funding programmes) to harness the potential of a European Network of Agroecology Living Labs and Research Infrastructures for accelerating transition to agroecology. These briefs use key results and insights from a European Network developed in the project, such as barriers and enablers of transition to agroecology (Thorsøe *et al.*, 2022; Thorsøe *et al.*, 2023), needs and the key end-users of the capacity building programme (Vervoort *et al.*, 2021), added value of a European Network (Schwarz *et al.*, 2022), competencies and skills for agroecology transition (Bijttebier *et al.*, 2022), key issues and principles for data management (Avila *et al.*, 2021, Caro *et al.*, 2023), lessons learnt on stakeholder engagement (Riedel *et al.*, 2023) and key issues and lessons learnt for the long-term sustainability of the European Network (Stojacic *et al.*, 2024, Schwarz *et al.*, 2024).

The aim of the briefs was to disseminate policy-related insights and recommendations based on knowledge gained in ALL-Ready, and facilitate the transfer of knowledge concerning the future European Network as part of the Horizon Europe Partnership “Accelerating farming systems transition: agroecology living labs and research infrastructures” (Partnership AGROECOLOGY). These publications are designed to be also of relevance to private funding organisations as well as communities of living labs and research infrastructures across Europe.

In line with the Communication and Dissemination Plan (Haller *et al.*, 2021; D7.1):

- **Policy briefs**, are targeted to policy-makers and funding organisations at European, national, regional and local levels;

Work on the development of the policy briefs was structured into two levels:

- **Policy briefs covering specific themes** disseminating key learnings and policy recommendations from the ALL-Ready work packages (WP). These briefs were developed by the WP lead partners and lead authors of the underlying deliverables, in collaboration with relevant partners. These policy briefs are reported in this deliverable.
- **Policy briefs covering cross-cutting issues at project level** to disseminate key lessons learnt and recommendations for improved public policies. These briefs were developed by a team coordinated under WP7 Communication and dissemination and **are reported in D7.3 Policy report**.

Selection of the topics of the policy briefs was informed by feedback from stakeholders involved in the regional workshops and the work undertaken with the pilot network. The set of policy briefs was organised as follows:

- Topics were chosen by screening the key findings from all WPs, brought together in Tasks 4.3 Co-construction of recommendations for long term success of AgroEcoLLNet and 4.4 Implementation plan to run the network and policy recommendations (Stojacic et al., 2024, Schwarz et al., 2024), Task 2.4 Summary of success factors and barriers (Thorsøe et al., 2023), Task 3.3 Drawing conclusions: Stakeholder recommendations for AgroEcoLLNet implementation (Riedel et al., 2023) and Task 5.3 Implementing the capacity building training Programme (Cavallo et al., 2024) to identify and prioritise topics relevant for development into briefs for policy-makers, adding new insights to the dialogue relating to sectoral policies (e.g. CAP strategic plans) and research policies and funding programmes (e.g. Horizon Europe at European level and national funding programmes such as BÖL in Germany). The topics of the policy briefs also contribute to developing or addressing needs which emerged from the community of living labs and research infrastructures engaged in transitions to agroecology across Europe.

The policy briefs have been published through project and other channels (e.g. ALL-Ready website, newsletter, social media, [Zenodo](#)). This included the communication and outreach channels and professional networks of project partners and the network of the consortium of the Partnership AGROECOLOGY.

2. Overview of policy briefs

The policy briefs are listed in Table 1, presented by topic and with links to copies hosted in the Zenodo repository.

Table 1 Overview of topics, dissemination channels and publication links

Title	Link to versions in Zenodo repository
Policy Brief: Accelerating agroecology transition using living labs: policy enablers and barriers	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10001865
The benefits of a European Network of Agroecology Living Labs and Research Infrastructures	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10001815
Systems thinking: an important competency for agroecology transition	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10001836
Building a FAIR Future in Agroecology: Data Strategy Recommendations for Living Labs and European Research Infrastructures	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10001857
Supporting the sustainable long-term implementation of a European Network of Agroecology Living Labs and Research Infrastructures	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10033336

Dissemination of policy briefs using project level channels of:

- i) Project website news items

- Example of a news item on policy briefs: <https://www.all-ready-project.eu/communication/news-events/news/the-all-ready-policy-briefs-have-been-published.html>
- ii) Final ALL-Ready project newsletter
- iii) Project social media channels
 - Postings on Facebook, LinkedIn and X. For example: https://twitter.com/ALLReady_EU/status/1722381583477338564
- iv) Final ALL-Ready conference
 - Accessible from the project booth at the final conference, together with other key outputs of ALL-Ready such as the pilot network booklet.
- v) Partnership AGROECOLOGY
 - Disseminated to partners of the Partnership consortium including ministries of the Member States, informed the preparation of activities of the Partnership including the first science-policy dialogue foreseen in 2024.

3. Concluding comments

A total of 8 policy briefs (5 covering specific themes at WP level and 3 on cross-cutting issues at project level, with the latter reported in D7.3) were produced by the ALL-Ready project. The information covered findings in each of WPs 1 to 6 (1. Mission and vision of the network, 2. Mapping, analysis and overview of existing mechanisms for carrying out participatory agroecological research and innovation including KPI's for the network, 3. Coordination of stakeholder engagement and the ALL-Ready pilot, 4. Implementation and sustainability of the network, 5. Capacity building and 6. Knowledge and data management), promoted and published through WP7 Communication and dissemination.

The content or process of preparation of the policy briefs cover the breadth of the objectives of the ALL-Ready project. The policy briefs provide recommendations that build on i) the agreement of key features of agroecological systems and agroecology living labs and research infrastructures (Objective 1), ii) insights on how they can contribute to addressing barriers and enables for agroecology transition (Objective 2), iii) key factors for the sustainable implementation of the European Network in the medium and long-term (Objective 3), iv) stakeholder needs for a capacity building programme and data and knowledge management strategy and principles for the future European network (Objective 4). The processes of working with stakeholders to develop the project activities and co-constructing its findings delivers on the project objective of improving the knowledge base for policy makers and to promote engagement among the community of living labs and research infrastructures and funders (Objective 5).

The briefings contribute to the legacy of the ALL-Ready project. They will be disseminated to relevant policy officers at the European Commission through the Project Policy Officer and colleagues and feed into the Partnership AGROECOLOGY (e.g. the first science-policy dialogue activities foreseen in the Partnership in 2024). At national and regional levels, they will be exploited by project partners through appropriate communication channels, supporting institutional activities with relevant stakeholders, post-project.

4. Acknowledgements

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5. References

Avila, J.M., Sáenz-Albanés, A.J., Loppin, C., González-Aranda, J.M. (2021). Standards and protocols for FAIR data management identification. Deliverable report D6.1. ALL-Ready Project.

Avila, J.M. *et al.* (2023). Data Principles and Strategy for AgroEcoLLNet. Deliverable report D6.5. ALL-Ready Project.

Bijttebier, J., Fosselle, S., Vervoort, K. (2022) Skills and competencies framework. Deliverable report D5.2, ALL-Ready Project

Cavallo, D., Couture, I., Fosselle, S.; Bijttebier, J. (2024) Report on the capacity building validation activity and workshops. Deliverable report D5.3. ALL-Ready Project.

Riedel, A., Hobeika, M., Frelih-Larsen, A., Varga, K., Fosselle, S., Bijttebier, J. (2023) Booklet on overall stakeholder recommendations for the implementation of the future European Agroecology LL and RI Network. Deliverable report D3.3. ALL-Ready Project.

Schwarz, G., Stojacic, I., Riedel, A., Fosselle, S.; Bijttebier, J., Gödel, B., Cavallo, D., Couture, I., McPhee, C., Varga, K., Csonka, V., Avila, J.M., Soto, I., Caro, D., Thorsøe, M.H., Berg, T., Trkulja, I., Haller, L., Moeskoop, B., Monteleone, D., McKhann, H., Mambrini-Doudet, M., Bonnet, O., Hobeika, M., Krywoszyńska, A. (2024) Guidance for the implementation plan for a European Network of Agroecology Living Labs and Research Infrastructures. Deliverable report D4.3. All-Ready project. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10728309>

Schwarz, G., Hobeika, M., Stojacic, I., Gödel, B., Perez, RC. (2022) Report on the added value of the European Network. Deliverable report D4.1. All-Ready project. 28 p, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7447971>

Stojacic, I., Schwarz, G., Riedel, A., Hobeika, M., Fosselle, S.; Bijttebier, J., Gödel, B., Cavallo, D., Couture, I., Haller, L. (2024) Report on the preconditions for the sustainability of the Network and recommendations for its long-term success. Deliverable report D4.2. ALL-Ready project. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10728338>

Thorsøe, M.H., Berg, T., Schwarz, G., Gödel, B. (2023) Towards a Network of European Agroecology Living Labs: Advancing the agroecology transition using living labs. Deliverable report D2.6. ALL-Ready project.

Thorsøe, M.H.; Iversen, S.; De Notaris, C.; Trkulja, I.; Berg, T.; Fosselle, S.; Bijttebier, J.; Kohler, E.; Gödel, B.; Avila, J.M.; Jónász, G.; Krywoszyńska, A.; Schwarz, G. (2022) Drivers of agroecology transition. Deliverable report D2.3. ALL-Ready project. <https://zenodo.org/record/8147044>

Vervoort, K.; Varga, K.; Fosselle, S.; Bijttebier, J.; Haller, L.; Schwarz, G.; Gödel, B.; McKhann, H.; Avila J.M.; Berg, T.; de Porrás, M.; Mambrini-Doudet, M. (2022) Report on mapped needs and the key end users of the capacity building programme. Deliverable report D5.1. ALL-Ready project. <https://zenodo.org/record/8154348>